

**THE ROLE OF THE CONTEXT IN REALIZATION OF THE NOTIONAL
STRUCTURE OF THE TEXT (ON THE BASE OF THE ENGLISH LANGUAGE)**

*S. Muinjonova*¹

Abstract:

The article dwells on linguistic research of the context as a basic element in determination of the notional structure of the text.

Key words: context, linguistic research, indication, analysis, textual elements, expressiveness, semantic relations.

doi: <https://doi.org/10.2024/cc33ee87>

Context is an important linguistic notion, the determination of which is paid much attention by the linguists.

The determination of the context is based on the following principle issues:

a) the possibility of existence of different types of context and those systematic relations, on the base of which the realization of syntagmatic features of language elements takes place;

b) interaction of the elements of different systems and subsystems of the language and those concrete units with the help of which semantic connections within the context can be seen;

c) relative completeness of utterance, its informative value that is connected with the total semantic reveal of the realized units.

The notion of the context is widely used in the practice and theory of linguistic and stylistic researches [Bates E., 2006]. Linguistic context as a direct surrounding of the word is an essential condition of a verbal actualization of the meaning of the word with the help of polysemy and homonymy. The compatibility of a precise word with its pointed minimum represents the minimal context, which is regarded as a context unit.

The special role is played by contextual connections of the words in the literary text, which is characterized by the plurality of meanings and the study of which demands determination of not only subjective-logical, but emotional, expressive and evaluative meanings as well. During interpretation of the word in the literary text we have to take into account both linguistic micro-context and macro-context. The right choice of such approach is confirmed by the practice and theory of translation, where equivalency is reached on the level of the text as a whole, and the word exists only in the context of all its use in the given text [I. Sorvali, 1999, p.609].

From formal and informative points, a context can be considered a semantic unity with the following elements – the core (realized word) and indicator (meaning).

¹ *Muinjonova Sabinabonu, student of SamSIFL*

Let us analyze the story by R. Mangum “Ideal murder”. The aim of the story is to consider the meaningful structure of the text and determine the place and functions of context in the text.

The story begins with characteristic features of the hero due to which he was loved and respected by the people. The description of every feature is represented as a word interpretation, where the word is a core, and its interpretation is an indicator, which reveals its content.

For example:

For 22 years Mark Melcher had walked from his drugstore to his house at exactly 5 o'clock. Methodical Mark was. For 22 years he had been greeted respectfully along the way by men and women who had grown old with him. Dignified Mark was. For 22 years he had stopped to put the heads of children and give them penny candies. Kindly Mark was. “Wouldn't hurt a fly...”

The context shows the attitude of people towards Mark. A man is usually judged by his deeds. The direct and reported speech describe the behavior of the hero and shows the conclusion to his character.

Then we see how the core and indicator change their places towards each other, and in this way, people give their own explanations to the behavior of the hero:

Mark was Willwoville's best-loved citizen, all right. People came to him with their troubles... He had a way about him, Mark had, so that you listened to his advice, and carried it out, and found yourself the better for it.

The expression “to be gone over him” and the word “awful” attract the reader's attention by their explanation. In both contexts, interpretation given in the first context with the help of synonymic expressions and in the second one with the description of reaction and behavior of the hero, interpretations are supported by the semantic repetition that creates semantic net:

1) “... she was dead in love...; she was gone over him. Not just in love... but crazy about him – like some women get over a man”.

2) awful, ugly, threatens, terrible, awful.

The context of the word “awful” becomes very important for the whole text as well:

Emily began to talk on something awful. Mark listened to her story, and while she was telling it his eyes got to looking mighty ugly... “he threatens to tell something he knows about me, Mr. Melcher. Something he says is terrible”. Mark cried. It was awful... He had made up his mind to kill Old Man Fellows, to confess, and to let them hang him if they wanted to”.

The word “confess” was met before but it is explained after the committing the crime: He was going to confess, and clear his conscience, and clear his conscience, and make his peace with God...

The explanation of the word “crazy” is ambiguous. The first part represents explanation expressed in direct and reported speech that describes Mark's behavior being the initial context:

Wild-looking and sort of glassy they were – like crazy people's eyes...

“Mark Melcher's going crazy”, he (the sheriff) said. He thinks he's killed Old Man Fellows.

Thus, the meaning of the text appears due to the contexts. The spreading of the elements of the context within the whole text is one of the achievement meanings of emotionality and expressiveness of the text.

References:

[1]. Amriddinova, N. (2022). *The role of context in realization of semantic structure of the text. Zien Journal of Social Sciences and Humanities*, 13, 60-63.

[2]. Амриддинова, Н. Ш. (2021). *Peculiarities of Supply and Difficulties in the Research of Variation of Phraseological Meaning in Vocabulary Articles. Международный журнал искусство слова*, 4(6).

[3]. Амриддинова, Н. Ш. (2011). *Актуализация денотативно-сигнификативной семантики фразеологических единиц (на материале английского языка). Вестник Челябинского государственного университета*, (10), 16-18.

[4]. Амриддинова, Н. Ш. (2021). *Peculiarities of Supply and Difficulties in the Research of Variation of Phraseological Meaning in Vocabulary Articles. Международный журнал искусство слова*, 4(6).

[5]. Amriddinova, N. S. (2021). *Extra-Linguistic Reasons for Semantic Variation of Phraseologisms. Theoretical & Applied Science Учредители: Теоретическая и прикладная наука*, (9), 652-654.

[6]. Amriddinova, N. S. (2020). *Some Aspects of Correlation in Semantic Actualization of Phraseological Units. Modern Views and Research*, 183.

[7]. Bates E. *Language and Context: the Acquisition of pragmatics*. – New York: Academic Press, 2006. – P. 17-18

[8]. Sorvali Irma. *Original texts and their translations//Psycholinguistics on the threshold of the year 2000. – Proceedings of the 5th International Society of Applied Psycholinguists. – Porto, 1999. – P. 607-609*